

RESULTS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PROPOSED PREOPERATIVE TRAINING FOR CHILDREN WITH CHD IN THE PRE-AND POSTOPERATIVE PERIOD.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12502587>

Key words: congenital heart disease, children, hospital, nutrition, physical development, Vitamin D, preoperative preparation.

Currently, congenital heart defects (CHD) occupy a leading position in terms of prevalence in comparison with other malformations in children and remain the leading cause of their death.

About 1.5 million children with CHD are born every year in the world (Saperova Ye. V., Vakhlova I. V.). Analysis of literature data also proves links between nutritional deficiencies and poor wound healing, reduced immunity, weakened muscle function during surgical interventions, and an increased risk of postoperative complications.

Physical development and nutritional deficiencies are common problems in children with congenital heart defects, regardless of the type of defect and the presence or absence of cyanosis. Children with this pathology are at high risk of developing nutritional deficiencies. Therapeutic nutrition and correction of protein-energy deficiency in children with congenital heart defects can improve the condition of patients after cardiac surgery.

According to the WHO definition, nutritional insufficiency ("nutritional insufficiency", "nutritional insufficiency") is a cellular imbalance between the nutrients that come from food and energy and the body's need for them to support life, growth and specific functions

In this regard, the aim of the study is to optimize the method of preoperative management of young children with congenital heart defects based on their physical development and biochemical parameters.

Materials and methods of research. The article presents an analysis of a prospective study of 142 children with CHD aged from 1 month to 3 years.

Depending on preoperative management, the children were assigned to study groups. The main group consisted of 102 children with CHD and comprehensive preoperative training. The comparison group included 40 children with CHD who were admitted to the clinic for surgical correction with generally accepted preoperative preparation.

After determining the state of physical development and biochemical parameters, children with CHD in the main study group were offered tactics for managing children with CHD in the preoperative period. In the comparison group, among children with CHD admitted for surgical correction, examinations were conducted according to the standard of management of children with CHD adopted in the clinic. In the main group, after the detection of moderate protein-energy malnutrition, nutrition correction was carried out with a change in the diet and the introduction of timely complementary foods, starting from 6 months.

In the determination of moderate and severe protein-energy malnutrition (PEM), therapeutic mixtures were also added in addition to rational nutrition, trimetabol and vitamin D. Therapeutic mixtures were selected on the recommendation of a gastroenterologist-nutritionist, these are easily digestible, balanced, hypoallergenic mixtures enriched with basic nutrients and triglycerides, based on deep whey protein hydrolysate. In terms of microelement composition, osmolarity and

protein utilization, these mixtures are close to breast milk. When comparing the physical development of children with CHD in the study groups, when they were admitted to the hospital for cardiac surgery correction of CHD, the following results were determined. In the main group of the study, when the preoperative preparation we proposed was performed for 3 ± 0.5 months, normal physical development indicators (Median) were determined significantly more often, in 36.6% of cases, compared to the comparison group in 20%, ($p < 0.05$). PEM, moderate exhaustion was determined in the main group, significantly less often, in 23.5% children with CHD, compared to the comparison group in 30% of cases ($p < 0.05$). Severe protein-energy malnutrition exhaustion was significantly more common in the comparison group, compared to 12.7% in the main group and 22.5% in the comparison group.

Comparative data on the physical development of children with CHD in the study groups in the preoperative period

	Main group of the CHD study		Comparison Group CHD comparison group (n=40)		
Risk of overweight	--		-		
	37				$p < 0.05$
PEM. Risk of attrition (mild)					
P					$p < 0.05$
					$p < 0.05$

When analyzing the percentage distribution of children with CHD in the study groups depending on MRI in the preoperative period. The following was determined: in the 1st subgroup (1-12 months) of the main and comparison groups, the MRI/age indicator $< - 3CO$ was 11.9%, compared to the comparison group 22.2%, $< - 2CO$ in 21.7% compared to 27.7%.

In the 2nd subgroup of the main and comparison groups (1-3 years), the MRI/age indicator was determined as follows: $< - 3CO$ was 13.3%, compared to the comparison group 27.7%, $< - 2CO$ was 25% compared to 31.8%. (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Distribution of children with CHD in the study groups depending on MRI in the preoperative period

Thus, children with CHD on the background of adequate management with the inclusion of nutrition correction had optimal indicators of physical development in the preoperative period, which contributed to a favorable course of the postoperative period.

When analyzing the results of level 25 (OH)D in the study groups in dynamics (preoperative and postoperative periods) in the study groups, it was determined that in the main group with complex management and adequate correction of vitamin D, a positive dynamics of increase in this indicator was determined from 29.2 ± 9.2 ng/ml to 45.9 ± 14.2 ng/ml. The results of the vitamin D index in the comparison group, where vitamin D correction was carried out without control, at the time in the preoperative period were significantly lower than in the group with vitamin D correction and amounted to 28.8 ± 12.1 ng/ml.

Figure 2. Indicator level 25 (OH)D (ng/ ml) in the dynamics of the study groups.

Timely and adequate correction of vitamin D improved growth parameters in children, which is important for children with CHD, with a lag in physical development.

Conclusions. Thus, adequate preoperative preparation with the use of specialized mixtures for therapeutic nutrition in children with various types of CHD, and vitamin D correction, made it possible to stop the further development of acute phase reaction in the postoperative period, as evidenced by the regression of CRP (19.7 mg / l-up to 2.1 mg/l). as well as an increase in the concentration of total protein (from 51.3±5.2 mg/l to 62.5±4.9 mg/L) and albumin (from 42.7±8.1 mg / L to 42.9±5.6 mg / L).

When conducting comprehensive preoperative training for children with CHD, the proportion of children with a lack of weight and height indicators significantly decreased to 18.7% in the preoperative period. In the postoperative period, physical development indicators also improved, and the activity of inflammation (CRP) decreased by 2.6 times in children under one year of age, and by 1.4 times in children under 3 years of age. In children in the 1-3-year-old age group, the proportion of children with Somatomedin levels close to the reference values increased 1.4 times, the length of stay of children after surgical correction in the ICU decreased by 4 days and the length of hospital stay by 6 days.

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